

Comparison of different approaches to calculate ideal speeds of sound and physico-chemical parameters of binary liquid mixtures

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Abstract : Various approaches used in literature for the calculation of ideal speeds of sound which are further used to evaluate the quantity which may be deviations in speeds of sound Δu or excess speeds of sound u^E have been analyzed for 2-methoxyethanol + 2-(2-alkoxyethoxy)ethanol binary liquid mixtures. Different numerical values are obtained for different approaches which will give rise to different interpretations of the results. Further, physico-chemical parameters for pure components and binary liquid mixtures have been calculated. Speeds of sound have also been estimated using theoretical models.

Keywords : Binary liquid mixtures, ideal speeds of sound, theoretical speeds of sound, physico-chemical parameters.

Introduction

In recent times, studies carried out on the interpretation of speeds of sound of binary liquid mixtures are mainly concerned with departure from their ideal values. From the literature it is revealed that these values for speed of sound of ideal mixtures are calculated in different ways with the help of different equations. As a result, different values of excess speeds of sound or deviations in speeds of sound are obtained. Consequently, it is helpful to understand various approaches that have been used to obtain ideal contribution to excess speeds of sound. Therefore, the evaluation of their excess counterparts and investigating in the light of new approximations based on detailed thermodynamic formulation are very significant for the interpretation of molecular interaction and critical for the expression of the behavior of various solvents. Subtle errors associated with these approaches have been illustrated for mixtures containing alkoxyalkanols. In the present study we have taken the already reported experimental data¹ by our group on 2-methoxyethanol (1) + 2-

(2-alkoxyethoxy)ethanol (2) mixtures at 298.15 K. This study aims to analyze and find the thermodynamically correct approach for these types of mixtures.

Thermodynamic properties of binary liquid mixtures containing alkoxyethanols as one of the component are of considerable interest as the variation of these properties with changing the alkyl chain length as well as polar head group in alkoxyethanols provides important information. Alkoxyethanols are a very interesting class of substances, owing to the presence of the O and OH groups in the same molecule, which allow self-association via inter- and intramolecular hydrogen bonds. Extensive work has been carried out on the measurements of thermodynamic properties of binary liquid mixtures containing alkoxyethanols as one of the components in our research group. In a continuing effort to extend our database and to get more knowledge on the behavior of alkoxyethanols, in this paper we report some physico-chemical parameters calculated from experimental speeds of sound values for binary liquid mixtures containing alkoxyethanols. Also,

theoretical values of speeds of sound are calculated with the help of various empirical relations.

Working equations :

Theory :

The excess quantity Z^E , by definition, represents the excess of the given property Z of a real mixture over Z^{id} , the value for an ideal mixture at the same temperature, pressure, and composition :

$$Z^E = Z - Z^{id} \quad (1)$$

The accuracy of values of Z^E depends not only on the accuracy of the experimental quantity Z but also on the accuracy of any approximation adopted in evaluating Z^{id} . A literature²⁻⁴ search has clearly revealed some misconceptions about the calculation of Z^{id} . These errors are generally due to incorrect formulation of the ideal mixing law.

Approximate approaches to ideal speeds of sound :

Numerous approximate ideal mixing rules have been proposed to estimate ideal speed of sound u^{id} . The methods differ and they are all approximate. For example, the ultrasonic speed in ideal liquid mixtures of organic compounds was considered to be the mass fraction w_i weighted average of those of the speeds in the pure components u_i^+ , and calculated from equation⁵ :

$$u^{id} = \sum_i w_i u_i^+ \quad (2)$$

where w_i and u_i are the weight fraction and speeds of sound of component i , respectively.

The most frequently encountered error has been the assumption that u^{id} is the mole fraction x_i weighted average of the values of its pure components u_i^+ with the following expression^{3,6-8} (approximation I) :

$$u^{id} = \sum_i x_i u_i^+ \quad (3)$$

With the use of eq. (3), the quantity calculated from eq. (1) is sometimes erroneously identified as an excess ultrasonic speed or 'apparent excess speed of sound', Δu . The 'excess' means that, for a binary liquid mixtures having ideal thermodynamic properties, thermodynamic does not require the ultrasonic speed to be a linear function of the mole fraction composition. These terms should be avoided in the discussion of Δu .

However, the u^{id} has sometimes been approximated

by the volume fraction average⁹ ϕ_i (approximation II) :

$$u^{id} = \sum_i \phi_i u_i^+ \quad (4)$$

Another approach was used to calculate the ideal speeds of sound behavior for the 2-methoxyethanol + 2-(2-alkoxyethoxy)ethanol mixtures (approximation III) :

$$u^{id} = [(\sum x_i \rho_i^+) \kappa_s^{id}]^{-1/2} \quad (5)$$

where x_i and ρ_i^+ are the mole fraction and densities of the component i and κ_s^{id} is the ideal isentropic compressibility for the binary liquid mixture.

Calculation of density in ideal mixtures has sometimes been equated¹⁰ by a volume-fraction averaging instead of mole fraction averaging. So, it appears that the approach based on eq. (5) is doubtful for defining an ideal thermodynamic value for the speed of sound in a mixture. The calculated values of u^E obtained from eqs. (1) and (5) for the same binary mixtures is in fact quite different from those of the other approaches described here.

The formulation of u^{id} is more complex; a thermodynamically sound equation was proposed¹⁰ (approximation IV) :

$$u^{id} = [\sum \phi_i^2 (C_{P,i}^*/C_{V,i}^*) (C_{V,m}^{id}/C_{P,m}^{id}) (1/w_i (u_i^*)^2)]^{-1/2} \quad (6)$$

where ϕ_i , $C_{P,i}^*$ and $C_{V,i}^*$ are volume fraction, isobaric heat capacity and isochoric heat capacity for i -th component, respectively. $C_{P,m}^{id}$ and $C_{V,m}^{id}$ are the ideal heat capacities.

This equation is a slightly simplified form of equation given by Van Dael and Vangeel¹¹. In so far as the Newton-Laplace equation is valid, the ideal ultrasonic speed u^{id} may be expressed correctly in terms of thermodynamic quantities of an ideal mixture (approximation V)¹² :

$$u^{id} = V_m^{id} [M_m K_{S,m}^{id}]^{-1/2} \quad (7)$$

This approach is the same as those used to determine the ideal isentropic compressibility. As per Benson-Kiyohara approach¹³, thermodynamic properties of an ideal mixture must be mutually related in the same way as those of pure components and real mixtures. So, the ideal isentropic compressibility $K_{S,m}^{id}$, and ideal molar isentropic compressibility $K_{S,m}^{id}$, are expressed by following relationships.

$$\kappa_S^{id} = \sum \phi_i \{ \kappa_{S,i}^* + TV_i^* (\alpha_{P,i}^*)^2 / C_{P,i}^* \} - T(\sum x_i V_i^*) \sum (\phi_i \alpha_{P,i}^*)^2 / \sum x_i C_{P,i}^* \quad (8)$$

$$K_{S,m}^{id} = \sum x_i [K_{S,i}^* - TA_{P,i}^* \{ (\sum x_i A_{P,i}^* / \sum x_i C_{P,i}^*) - (A_{P,i}^* / C_{P,i}^*) \}] \quad (9)$$

where ϕ_i and x_i are the volume fraction and mole fraction of component i in the mixture, respectively. $A_{P,i}^*$ is the product of molar volume V_i^* and the isobaric expansivity $\alpha_{P,i}^*$, $C_{P,i}^*$ is the isobaric molar heat capacity, and $K_{S,i}^*$ are the properties of the pure liquid component i , respectively.

This approach is the same as those used to determine the ideal isentropic compressibility. Using eq. (7), the quantity calculated from eq. (1) is sometimes called the

deviation of ultrasonic speed¹⁴ Δu , which seems to be more correct. In literatures, this quantity was referred to as an ‘excess’ ultrasonic speed. It is not appropriate to speak of an excess intensive property^{15,16}. The literature¹⁷⁻²⁰ values of the parameters required for estimation of these approximations are given in Table S1 in the form of supplementary content. The variations of the values of u^E for 2-methoxyethanol + 2-(2-alkoxyethoxy)ethanol mixtures based on all five approximations are reported in Table 1 and are also shown in Fig. 1 only for 2-methoxyethanol (1) + 2-(2-methoxyethoxy)ethanol (2) mixture.

Table S1. Values of densities (ρ), product $A_{P,m}$ of the molar volume and the isobaric thermal expansivity, molar isobaric heat capacities ($C_{P,m}$), ultrasonic speeds (u), and the product $K_{S,m}$ of the molar volume and isentropic compressibility of pure liquid components at 298.15 K

Component	$\rho \times 10^{-3}$ (kg m ⁻³)	$A_{P,m}$ (mm ³ K ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹)	$C_{P,m}$ (J K ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹)	u (m s ⁻¹)	$K_{S,m}$ (mm ³ mol ⁻¹ MPa ⁻¹)
2-Methoxyethanol	0.9602 ¹	72.9 ¹⁷	176.4 ¹⁷	1341.3 ¹	45.88
2-(2-Methoxyethoxy)ethanol	1.0164 ¹	100.4 ¹	271.1 ¹⁸	1415.5 ¹	58.05
2-(2-Ethoxyethoxy)ethanol	0.9839 ¹	115.4 ¹⁹	298.1 ¹⁹	1385.2 ¹	72.22
2-(2-Butoxyethoxy)ethanol	0.9479 ¹	144.2 ¹⁹	358.4 ¹⁹	1356.4 ¹	98.14

Table 1. Excess or deviations in speeds of sound for mixture 2-methoxyethanol (1) + 2-(2-alkoxyethoxy)ethanol (2) mixtures at 298.15 K calculated by different approximations

x_1	u^E or Δu (m s ⁻¹) calculated from approximation					<i>Table-1 (contd.)</i>					
	I	II	III	IV	V						
						0.4006	9.32	2.56	2.02	4.00	5.69
						0.4466	9.65	2.45	1.92	3.95	5.76
						0.4895	9.72	2.43	1.93	3.95	5.88
						0.5336	9.79	2.41	1.94	3.89	5.94
						0.5690	9.82	2.44	2.01	3.86	6.00
0.0010	0.07	0.05	0.10	-0.43	0.11	0.6060	9.77	2.47	2.08	3.79	6.02
0.0019	0.24	0.19	0.13	-0.27	0.27	0.6441	9.59	2.48	2.13	3.65	5.98
0.0036	0.47	0.38	0.31	-0.08	0.47	0.6914	9.00	2.24	1.97	3.17	5.62
0.0047	0.65	0.53	0.47	0.09	0.63	0.7390	8.13	1.90	1.68	2.50	5.07
0.0070	0.82	0.65	0.57	0.22	0.78	0.7945	7.15	1.74	1.60	1.85	4.54
0.0106	1.59	1.33	1.24	0.92	1.49	0.8332	5.92	1.24	1.14	0.92	3.70
0.0149	2.11	1.74	1.65	1.37	1.95	0.8797	4.57	0.93	0.88	0.01	2.88
0.0222	2.25	1.71	1.60	1.79	1.99	0.9223	3.23	0.72	0.70	-0.85	2.10
0.0325	2.71	1.93	1.79	1.68	2.30	0.9518	2.22	0.59	0.59	-1.49	1.51
0.0449	3.03	1.97	1.79	1.80	2.47	0.9735	1.53	0.60	0.61	-1.88	1.16
0.0557	3.43	2.12	1.92	2.03	2.72	0.9839	1.21	0.63	0.64	-2.06	1.00
0.0724	3.77	2.09	1.85	2.10	2.85	0.9919	0.90	0.61	0.61	-2.24	0.82
0.0916	4.40	2.30	2.02	2.43	3.24	0.9951	1.04	0.86	0.86	-2.06	1.01
0.1072	4.85	2.43	2.12	2.66	3.51	0.9968	0.96	0.85	0.85	-2.11	0.97
0.1629	5.99	2.46	2.06	3.02	4.03	0.9981	0.66	0.59	0.59	-2.39	0.68
0.2116	6.90	2.52	2.05	3.32	4.47	0.9992	0.44	0.41	0.42	-2.59	0.48
0.2747	7.88	2.53	2.01	3.61	4.94	0.9997	0.08	0.07	0.07	-2.95	0.14
0.3287	8.69	2.64	2.10	3.91	5.40						

Table-1 (contd.)

2-Methoxyethanol (1) + 2-(2-ethoxyethoxy)ethanol (2)					
0.0011	0.15	0.13	0.06	-2.39	0.01
0.0026	0.21	0.17	0.07	-2.35	0.04
0.0043	0.39	0.31	0.08	-2.20	0.18
0.0055	0.54	0.44	0.09	-2.07	0.31
0.0072	0.62	0.48	0.10	-2.02	0.36
0.0133	0.78	0.54	0.11	-1.95	0.42
0.0160	0.80	0.57	0.12	-1.98	0.41
0.0199	0.97	0.61	0.11	-1.87	0.42
0.0337	1.48	0.87	0.39	-1.58	0.80
0.0536	1.95	1.00	0.19	-1.41	0.98
0.0719	2.36	1.09	0.48	-1.28	1.11
0.1011	2.94	1.19	1.28	-1.12	1.28
0.1568	3.98	1.38	1.65	-0.85	1.58
0.2093	4.79	1.45	1.39	-0.66	1.77
0.2715	5.52	1.42	1.51	-0.59	1.86
0.3402	6.23	1.42	1.07	-0.48	1.98
0.4006	6.69	1.38	0.46	-0.45	2.04
0.4499	6.95	1.34	0.77	-0.45	2.06
0.5056	7.20	1.36	0.90	-0.69	2.16
0.5598	7.18	1.26	0.87	-0.49	2.09
0.6113	6.04	1.16	0.03	-0.45	1.02
0.6623	6.77	1.08	0.14	-0.70	1.95
0.6969	6.49	1.01	1.03	-0.82	1.87
0.7406	6.01	0.89	1.31	-1.00	1.72
0.7834	5.39	0.75	1.78	-1.24	1.52
0.8272	4.61	0.59	2.88	-1.53	1.30
0.8784	3.56	0.45	4.08	-1.86	0.96
0.9350	2.15	0.31	1.89	-2.28	0.69
0.9621	1.44	0.31	1.20	-2.44	0.57
0.9785	0.94	0.30	2.48	-2.56	0.48
0.9889	0.61	0.27	0.39	-2.67	0.39
0.9936	0.42	0.22	0.06	-2.75	0.32
0.9951	0.38	0.23	0.18	-2.75	0.32
0.9967	0.26	0.15	0.09	-2.84	0.23
0.9979	0.21	0.14	0.08	-2.86	0.21
0.9984	0.13	0.08	0.03	-2.93	0.15
0.9991	0.16	0.13	0.10	-2.88	0.21
0.9996	0.08	0.07	0.11	-2.95	0.14

2-Methoxyethanol(1) + 2-(2-butoxyethoxy)ethanol (2)					
0.0004	0.006	0.003	0.1	2.05	0.03
0.0015	0.02	0.01	0.1	2.06	0.04
0.0021	0.02	0.02	0.1	2.06	0.04
0.0027	0.14	0.12	0.1	2.16	0.05
0.0037	0.16	0.13	0.1	2.17	0.16
0.0048	0.17	0.13	0.2	2.17	0.16

Table-1 (contd.)

0.0058	0.19	0.14	0.2	2.18	0.17
0.0078	0.32	0.26	0.3	2.29	0.28
0.0091	0.34	0.26	0.3	2.29	0.30
0.0110	0.47	0.38	0.4	2.40	0.41
0.0134	0.60	0.49	0.6	2.51	0.52
0.0181	0.67	0.53	0.6	2.53	0.56
0.0239	0.76	0.57	0.7	2.56	0.60
0.0360	0.84	0.56	0.7	2.52	0.59
0.0506	0.76	0.36	0.6	2.28	0.40
0.0800	0.71	0.08	0.5	1.93	0.12
0.1051	0.78	-0.02	0.5	1.75	0.02
0.1522	0.79	-0.34	0.3	1.29	-0.29
0.2013	0.94	-0.52	0.4	0.96	-0.47
0.2488	0.96	-0.79	0.3	0.54	-0.73
0.2998	0.93	-1.10	0.1	0.06	-1.03
0.3533	0.87	-1.43	0.1	-0.47	-0.47
0.4146	0.66	-1.87	-0.4	-1.14	-1.78
0.4804	0.55	-2.17	-0.5	-1.72	-2.08
0.5567	0.21	-2.65	-0.9	-2.55	-2.55
0.6369	-0.18	-3.03	-1.3	-3.35	-2.92
0.7116	-0.65	-3.35	-1.7	-4.09	-3.23
0.7758	-0.69	-3.10	-1.7	-4.26	-2.99
0.8321	-0.64	-2.68	-1.5	-4.24	-2.57
0.8941	-0.30	-1.78	-0.9	-3.82	-1.68
0.9346	0.01	-0.98	-0.4	-3.38	-0.89
0.9677	0.41	-0.12	0.2	-2.82	-0.04
0.9862	0.59	0.36	0.5	-2.52	0.42
0.9956	0.63	0.56	0.6	-2.42	0.62
0.9974	0.36	0.32	0.3	-2.68	0.38
0.9991	0.19	0.17	0.2	-2.84	0.23
0.9996	0.09	0.09	0.1	-2.93	0.15

Fig. 1. Variation of excess or deviations in speeds of sound obtained from ideal speeds of sound calculated by different approximations for 2-methoxyethanol (1) + 2-(2-methoxyethoxy)ethanol (2) at 298.15 K.

The values of u^E obtained from approximation I are highly positive and values obtained from approximation IV are more on negative side for all the mixtures. The u^E values obtained from approximations II and III are quite close to each other for 2-(2-methoxyethoxy)ethanol and 2-(2-ethoxyethoxy)ethanol while u^E values obtained from approximations II and V are close to each other for 2-methoxyethanol + 2-(2-butoxyethoxy)ethanol mixtures. Also, the values of u^E obtained from all the approximations are positive and negative for 2-methoxyethanol + 2-(2-butoxyethoxy)ethanol mixtures. The values obtained from approximations I and V are showing greater deviations in comparison to all other approximations for all the mixtures. From the present study, it is observed that different magnitude of values is obtained using different approximations. Same approaches have also been analyzed earlier^{10,21-23} for other type of binary liquid mixtures which again shows same type of behaviour. Our main aim to the present study is to highlight and show the

of sound and density data. Various parameters such as intermolecular free length²⁴ L_f , available volume²⁵ V_a , molar sound velocity²⁵ R , collision factor²⁶ S , acoustic impedance²⁷ Z , relative association²⁸ R_A and molecular association²⁹ M_A have been calculated using the following relations :

$$L_f = K/(u\rho^{1/2}) \quad (10)$$

$$V_a = V(1 - u/u_\infty) \quad (11)$$

$$R = Mu^{1/3}/\rho \quad (12)$$

$$Z = \rho u \quad (13)$$

$$R_A = (\rho_{\text{mix}}/\rho)(u/u_{\text{mix}})^{1/3} \quad (14)$$

$$M_A = [(u_{\text{mix}}/\sum x_i u_i)^2 - 1] \quad (15)$$

where L_f is the free length of ideal mixing, K is a temperature dependent constant $\{ (= (93.875 + 0.375T) \times 10^{-8})^{23}$, u_∞ is taken as 1600 m s^{-1} . These parameters are listed in Table 2 for the pure components. The values for binary liquid mixtures are shown in Figs. S1-S6.

Table 2. Values of derived parameters of the pure liquid components at 298.15 K

Component	$B \times 10^6$ ($\text{m}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1}$)	S	$R \times 10^3$ ($\text{m}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} (\text{m s}^{-1})^{1/3}$)	$V_a \times 10^6$ ($\text{m}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1}$)	L_f (\AA)
2-Methoxyethanol	19.28	3.45	874	12.81	0.4949
2-(2-Methoxyethoxy)ethanol	28.72	3.64	1327	13.63	0.4558
2-(2-Ethoxyethoxy)ethanol	33.14	3.56	1520	18.31	0.4734
2-(2-Butoxyethoxy)ethanol	41.81	3.47	1895	26.06	0.4925

variation in results with the use of different approximations, i.e. why five approximations are used and the results are reported. The outcome of the analysis reveals that approximations IV and V are well established and thermodynamically consistent relations. But many times it is seen while going through literature that simple ideal mixing laws i.e. mole fraction weighted average and volume fraction weighted average on the lines of approximations I and II are being used which may be due to either lack of data like α or C_p values for applying approximations IV and V or lack of awareness.

Physico-chemical parameters from speeds of sound data :

We have attempted to explain the physico-chemical behavior of the mixtures in order to explore the strength and nature of the interactions between the components by deriving various thermodynamic parameters from the speed

Fig. S1. Variation of intermolecular free length (L_f) for 2-methoxyethanol (1) + 2-(2-methoxyethoxy)ethanol (2) (o); + 2-(2-ethoxyethoxy)ethanol (2) (Δ); + 2-(2-butoxyethoxy)ethanol (2) (\square) at 298.15 K.

It is observed from the data¹ that u , V_a , Z , R decreases with mole fraction of x while L_f increases. In case of R_A , values increase for 2-(2-ethoxyethoxy)ethanol and 2-(2-

Fig. S2. Variation of available volume (V_A) for 2-methoxyethanol (1) + 2-(2-methoxyethoxy)ethanol (2) (o); + 2-(2-ethoxyethoxy)ethanol (2) (Δ); + 2-(2-butoxyethoxy)ethanol (2) (□) at 298.15 K.

Fig. S5. Variation of relative association parameter (R_A) for 2-methoxyethanol (1) + 2-(2-methoxyethoxy)ethanol (2) (o); + 2-(2-ethoxyethoxy)ethanol (2) (Δ); + 2-(2-butoxyethoxy)ethanol (2) (□) at 298.15 K.

Fig. S3. Variation of molar sound velocity (R) for 2-methoxyethanol (1) + 2-(2-methoxyethoxy)ethanol (2) (o); + 2-(2-ethoxyethoxy)ethanol (2) (Δ); + 2-(2-butoxyethoxy)ethanol (2) (□) at 298.15 K.

Fig. S6. Variations of molecular association (M_A) for 2-methoxyethanol (1) + 2-(2-methoxyethoxy)ethanol (2) (o); + 2-(2-ethoxyethoxy)ethanol (2) (Δ); + 2-(2-butoxyethoxy)ethanol (2) (□) at 298.15 K.

Fig. S4. Variation of acoustic impedance (Z) for 2-methoxyethanol (1) + 2-(2-methoxyethoxy)ethanol (2) (o); + 2-(2-ethoxyethoxy)ethanol (2) (Δ); + 2-(2-butoxyethoxy)ethanol (2) (□) at 298.15 K.

butoxyethoxy)ethanol mixtures, it decreases for 2-(2-methoxyethoxy)ethanol with increase in the mole fraction of 2-methoxyethanol. Relatively higher values of R_A for 2-methoxyethanol + 2-(2-methoxyethoxy)ethanol system, signifies that unlike interactions are relatively strong compared to like interactions. Similarly, larger deviations in M_A for 2-methoxyethanol + 2-(2-methoxyethoxy)ethanol system decrease with increase in the alkyl chain length of 2-(2-alkoxyethoxy)ethanol. Thus it is concluded that non ideality of the system varies in the order 2-(2-methoxyethoxy)ethanol > 2-(2-ethoxyethoxy)ethanol > 2-(2-butoxyethoxy)ethanol.

The deviations in intermolecular free length L_f and acoustic impedance Z were calculated using the relation

$$\Delta L_f = L_f - [xL_{f,1} + (1-x)L_{f,2}] \quad (16)$$

$$\Delta Z = Z - [xZ_1 + (1-x)Z_2] \quad (17)$$

The results of ΔL_f and ΔZ are plotted in Figs. 2 and 3 respectively against the mole fraction of 2-methoxyethanol.

Fig. 2. Variation of deviations in intermolecular free length (ΔL_f) for 2-methoxyethanol (1) + 2-(2-methoxyethoxy)ethanol (2) (o); + 2-(2-ethoxyethoxy)ethanol (2) (Δ); + 2-(2-butoxyethoxy)ethanol (2) (\square) at 298.15 K.

Fig. 3. Variation of deviation in acoustic impedance (ΔZ) for 2-methoxyethanol (1) + 2-(2-methoxyethoxy)ethanol (2) (o); + 2-(2-ethoxyethoxy)ethanol (2) (Δ); + 2-(2-butoxyethoxy)ethanol (2) (\square) at 298.15 K.

ΔL_f values are negative for mixtures 2-(2-methoxyethoxy)ethanol and 2-(2-ethoxyethoxy)ethanol, and is positive with the 2-(2-butoxyethoxy)ethanol. The values change sign at lower and higher mole fractions for all the mixtures. Same behavior but with opposite sign is observed for ΔZ values. The values are positive for mixtures 2-(2-methoxyethoxy)ethanol and 2-(2-ethoxyethoxy)-

ethanol, and is negative with the 2-(2-butoxyethoxy)-ethanol. Also, the behavior of excess molar volumes³⁰, excess molar isentropic compressibilities and deviations u^D of speeds of sound from their ideal values¹ seems to be consistent with a minimum value of ΔL_f and a maximum value for ΔZ .

Negative and positive deviations in these functions from rectilinear dependence on mole fraction indicate the extent of association between unlike molecules. A minimum value of $K_{S,m}^E$ and ΔL_f and a maximum value of u^D are observed for 2-methoxyethanol + 2-(2-methoxyethoxy)ethanol. This is normal because u is generally higher when the system has higher rigidity. Negative values of ΔZ with x are indicative of decreasing strength of interaction between component molecules of the mixtures.

Estimation of speeds of sound :

The speeds of sound values have been estimated for mixtures studied in the present study by using several theoretical models like Jacobson's free length theory²⁴, Schaaff's collision factor theory²⁵, Junjie model²⁶ and Nomoto model³¹.

As per Jacobson's free length theory, speeds of sound are given as

$$u_{FLT} = K/(L_f \rho^{1/2}) \quad (18)$$

In terms of Schaaff's collision factor theory, speeds of sound are given by

$$u_{CFT} = u_\infty \{x_1 S_1 + x_2 S_2\} [\{x_1 B_1 + x_2 B_2\}/V] \quad (19)$$

where $S = uV/u_\infty B$ is the collision factor and B is the geometrical volume i.e. actual volume of the molecule per mole. The values of S and B are given in Table 2.

Junjie model describes the speeds of sound as

$$u_j = \{x_1 M_1/\rho_1 + x_2 M_2/\rho_2\} / [\{x_1 M_1 + x_2 M_2\}^{1/2} \{ (x_1 M_1/\rho_1 u_1^2) + x_2 M_2/\rho_2 u_2^2 \}^{1/2}] \quad (20)$$

where the symbols have their usual meanings.

As per Nomoto model, speeds of sound are given as

$$u_N = [\{x_1 R_1 + x_2 R_2\} / \{x_1 V_1 + x_2 V_2\}]^3 \quad (21)$$

where R and V are the molar sound velocity and molar volume respectively.

The estimated speeds of sound viz. u_{FLT} , u_{CFT} , u_j and u_N values are reported in Table S2 and are also shown in Fig. 4 only for 2-methoxyethanol + 2-(2-methoxyethoxy)ethanol binary liquid mixture as other mixtures

Fig. 4. Experimental and calculated speeds of sound (u) for 2-methoxyethanol (1) + 2-(2-methoxyethoxy)ethanol (2) at 298.15 K.

Table-S2 (contd.)

0.7390	1361.72	1379.72	1366.34	988.28
0.7945	1357.72	1377.52	1361.48	990.80
0.8332	1354.93	1375.94	1357.96	992.48
0.8797	1351.58	1374.01	1353.57	994.43
0.9223	1348.52	1372.21	1349.39	996.13
0.9518	1346.39	1370.93	1346.39	997.26
0.9735	1344.83	1369.99	1344.14	998.06
0.9839	1344.08	1369.53	1343.05	998.43
0.9919	1343.50	1369.18	1342.20	998.72
0.9951	1343.27	1369.03	1341.85	998.83
0.9968	1343.15	1368.96	1341.67	998.89
0.9981	1343.06	1368.90	1341.53	998.94
0.9992	1342.98	1368.85	1341.42	998.98
0.9997	1342.94	1368.83	1341.36	998.99
1.0000	1342.92	1368.82	1341.33	999.00

Table S2. Values of the speeds of sound u estimated from theoretical models at 298.15 K for the binary mixtures 2-methoxyethanol (1) + 2-(2-alkoxyethoxy)ethanol (2) at 298.15 K

x_1	u_{CFT}	u_{Junjie}	u_{nomoto}	u_{FLT}	2-Methoxyethanol (1) + 2-(2-ethoxyethoxy)ethanol (2)				
0.0000	1414.90	1404.03	1414.66	946.82	0.0000	1384.21	1396.49	1384.73	967.32
0.0010	1414.91	1404.01	1414.61	946.68	0.0011	1348.16	1396.47	1384.70	967.36
0.0019	1414.85	1403.98	1414.56	946.74	0.0026	1384.10	1396.44	1384.66	967.42
0.0036	1414.73	1403.93	1414.48	946.85	0.0043	1384.03	1396.41	1384.62	967.48
0.0047	1414.65	1403.90	1414.42	946.92	0.0055	1383.98	1396.39	1384.59	967.53
0.0070	1414.48	1403.84	1414.31	947.06	0.0072	1383.91	1396.36	1384.55	967.59
0.0106	1414.22	1403.94	1414.13	947.29	0.0133	1383.66	1396.26	1384.39	967.82
0.0149	1413.91	1403.62	1413.91	947.56	0.0160	1383.55	1396.21	1384.32	967.92
0.0222	1413.38	1403.42	1413.54	948.03	0.0199	1383.39	1396.14	1384.22	968.07
0.0325	1412.64	1403.13	1413.02	948.68	0.0337	1382.82	1395.90	1383.86	968.58
0.0449	1411.74	1402.79	1412.38	949.46	0.0536	1382.00	1395.55	1383.33	969.32
0.0557	1410.96	1402.48	1411.82	950.15	0.0719	1381.25	1395.21	1382.84	970.00
0.0724	1409.76	1402.01	1410.95	951.19	0.1011	1398.05	1394.68	1382.04	971.07
0.0916	1408.37	1404.46	1409.94	952.39	0.1568	1377.77	1393.62	1380.46	973.11
0.1072	1407.25	1401.01	1409.11	953.36	0.2093	1375.61	1392.57	1378.89	975.00
0.1629	1403.23	1399.38	1406.06	956.80	0.2715	1373.05	1391.28	1376.94	977.21
0.2116	1399.72	1397.92	1403.31	959.75	0.3402	1370.22	1389.76	1374.64	979.61
0.2747	1395.17	1395.98	1399.60	963.52	0.4006	1367.74	1388.36	1372.50	981.68
0.3287	1391.29	1394.27	1396.29	966.68	0.4499	1365.71	1387.15	1370.65	983.34
0.4006	1386.11	1391.93	1391.69	970.78	0.5056	1363.43	1385.72	1368.44	985.19
0.4466	1382.80	1390.38	1388.62	973.35	0.5598	1361.21	1384.26	1366.17	986.94
0.4895	1379.70	1388.91	1385.66	975.69	0.6113	1359.09	1382.80	1363.89	988.56
0.5336	1376.53	1387.37	1382.51	978.05	0.6623	1357.00	1381.27	1361.50	990.12
0.5690	1373.97	1386.10	1379.91	979.91	0.6969	1355.58	1380.19	1359.79	991.16
0.6060	1371.31	1384.76	1377.11	981.80	0.7406	1353.78	1378.78	1357.54	992.43
0.6441	1368.56	1383.35	1374.14	983.72	0.7834	1352.01	1377.32	1355.22	993.64
0.6914	1365.15	1381.56	1370.33	986.03	0.8272	1350.19	1375.76	1352.72	994.83
					0.8784	1348.05	1373.04	1349.59	996.17
					0.9350	1345.68	1371.59	1345.92	997.55
					0.9621	1344.54	1370.46	1344.06	998.17

Table-S2 (contd.)

0.9785	1343.84	1369.76	1342.89	998.54
0.9889	1343.40	1369.31	1342.14	998.77
0.9936	1343.19	1369.10	1341.80	998.87
0.9951	1343.13	1369.03	1341.09	998.90
0.9967	1343.06	1368.96	1341.57	998.93
0.9979	1343.01	1368.91	1341.48	998.96
0.9984	1342.99	1368.89	1341.45	998.97
0.9991	1342.96	1368.86	1341.40	998.99
0.9996	1342.94	1368.83	1341.36	999.00
1.0000	1342.92	1368.82	1341.33	999.00
2-Methoxyethanol (1) + 2-(2-butoxyethoxy)ethanol (2)				
0.0000	1356.32	1393.18	1357.47	987.77
0.0004	1356.32	1393.17	1357.46	987.77
0.0015	1356.31	1393.16	1357.45	987.78
0.0021	1356.30	1393.15	1357.45	987.78
0.0027	1356.29	1393.15	1357.45	987.79
0.0037	1356.28	1393.14	1357.44	987.79
0.0048	1356.27	1393.12	1357.43	987.80
0.0058	1356.26	1393.11	1357.42	987.81
0.0078	1356.23	1393.09	1357.41	987.83
0.0091	1356.22	1393.07	1357.40	987.83
0.0110	1356.20	1393.05	1357.38	987.85
0.0134	1356.17	1393.02	1357.36	987.87
0.0181	1356.11	1392.97	1357.33	987.90
0.0239	1356.05	1392.90	1357.28	987.94
0.0360	1355.91	1392.76	1357.19	988.04
0.0506	1355.74	1392.58	1357.08	988.15
0.0800	1355.39	1392.22	1356.84	988.37
0.1051	1355.10	1391.90	1356.63	988.56
0.1522	1354.54	1391.28	1356.22	988.93
0.2013	1353.94	1390.59	1355.78	989.32
0.2488	1353.34	1389.89	1355.32	987.71
0.2998	1352.69	1389.09	1354.79	990.14
0.3533	1351.98	1388.19	1354.20	990.60
0.4146	1351.16	1387.08	1353.48	991.15
0.4804	1350.25	1385.78	1352.62	991.77
0.5567	1349.19	1384.12	1351.53	992.54
0.6369	1348.06	1382.15	1350.23	993.42
0.7116	1346.99	1380.08	1348.86	994.33
0.7758	1346.08	1378.07	1347.53	995.18
0.8321	1345.27	1376.12	1346.23	996.00
0.8941	1344.39	1373.71	1344.63	997.00
0.9346	1343.82	1371.96	1343.47	997.72
0.9677	1343.36	1370.43	1342.44	998.34
0.9862	1343.11	1369.52	1341.83	998.71
0.9956	1342.98	1369.04	1341.51	998.91

Table-S2 (contd.)

0.9974	1342.95	1368.95	1341.45	998.95
0.9991	1342.93	1368.86	1341.39	998.98
0.9996	1342.93	1368.84	1341.37	998.99
1.0000	1342.92	1368.82	1341.36	999.00

show same type of behavior for comparison with experimental values for all the mixtures. The results clearly indicate that simple Nomoto expression and collision factor theory predict the experimental data¹ extremely well for all the mixtures. Speeds of sound values calculated by Junjie expression shows some deviations from the experimental values while free length theory is not predicting the experimental data very well as it shows greater deviations from the experimental data.

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